

ROLE OF CINNAMON COMPOUNDS IN GLYCEMIC CONTROL AND DIABETES MANAGEMENT

Nimra Sharif¹, Eman Khalid², Amina Arif³, Fatima ul Zohra⁴, Ujala Arshad⁵,
Hussnain Bismil⁶, Usman Wajid⁷

^{1,2,3,4,5,6}Department of Basic & Applied Chemistry, Faculty of Science & Technology, University of Central Punjab
Lahore.

⁷University Institute of Biochemistry & Biotechnology, Pir Mehr Ali Shah Arid Agriculture University Rawalpindi.

³draminaarif@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15590288>

Keywords

Article History

Received on 26 April 2025

Accepted on 26 May 2025

Published on 04 June 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Amina Arif

Abstract

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by elevated blood glucose levels, resulting from either insulin resistance or insufficient insulin production. Insulin resistance, particularly in Type 2 Diabetes, leads to impaired glucose metabolism and worsened insulin sensitivity. Cinnamon, known for its therapeutic properties, has been investigated for its potential to alleviate insulin resistance and improve glucose uptake. This study explores the impact of *C. cassia* extract on diabetic patients, particularly focusing on its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and anti-diabetic properties. The *C. cassia* bark was extracted using methanol and ethanol, followed by qualitative and quantitative analyses to identify key phytochemicals such as polyphenols, flavonoids, and cinnamaldehyde. These compounds were found to significantly enhance insulin sensitivity and lower blood glucose levels. Antioxidant activity was assessed using the DPPH assay, showing promising radical scavenging effects, particularly in the ethanolic extract. Anti-diabetic activity was confirmed through alpha-amylase inhibition, while antimicrobial testing demonstrated significant inhibition against *S. aureus*. The results suggest that *C. cassia* extract, particularly its methanolic form, holds great promise as a natural, cost-effective adjunct to diabetes management, offering benefits in glucose regulation, wound healing, and infection prevention. The findings provide strong evidence for the potential role of cinnamon as a complementary therapy in diabetes care, contributing to a holistic approach for managing the disease and its complications.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes is a chronic condition where the body either doesn't produce enough insulin or cannot use it effectively, leading to high blood sugar (Global Burden of Disease Collaborative Network, 2020). Insulin regulates blood sugar and metabolism of carbohydrates, fats, and proteins (Poznyak et al., 2020). Poorly managed diabetes can cause hyperglycemia, damaging blood vessels and nerves. In 2019, it caused about 1.5 million deaths, nearly

half under age 70. Over two decades, the global age-standardized death rate rose by 3%, with a 13% increase in lower-middle-income countries. Regular care is vital to prevent complications and improve life quality.

Insulin resistance in diabetes disrupts metabolism in the liver, muscles, and fat tissues. Symptoms vary by type and disease duration, including excessive hunger, thirst, urination, weight loss, and vision

issues, especially in youth with low insulin levels (Rossi et al., 2019). Early type 2 diabetes may be symptomless. Severe hyperglycemia can lead to confusion or coma, and rarely, untreated diabetes can cause death from ketoacidosis or hyperosmolar syndrome (Poznyak et al., 2020).

The American Diabetes Association classifies diabetes into four main types: type 1, type 2, various specific forms, and gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM). Wilkin's accelerator hypothesis suggests that type 1 and type 2 diabetes may be different expressions of the same issue—insulin resistance—in individuals with different genetic backgrounds (Kahanovitz, Sluss, & Russell, 2017).

In type 1 diabetes, symptoms and a decline in insulin levels can begin up to two years before diagnosis.

Initially, insulin secretion increases as a compensatory response but rapidly declines after diagnosis, especially in the first year. Eventually, insulin production becomes minimal or absent. Even with normal blood sugar levels, significant fluctuations may indicate T1D. Monitoring markers like blood glucose and C-peptide can help assess risk (Kahanovitz, Sluss, & Russell, 2017).

In type 2 diabetes, insulin secretion defects are key. Insulin output varies based on sensitivity, and low disposition indices reflect poor compensation for insulin resistance. Obese individuals with T2D may have higher insulin levels than lean individuals, but it's insufficient due to significant insulin resistance (Galicia-Garcia et al., 2020).

Figure 1. Diabetes mellitus: types, inflammation-related complications, and the interactions between organs in T2D

Type 2 diabetes, which accounts for about 95% of all diabetes cases globally, worsens over time due to the gradual decline in beta-cell function, leading to persistent hyperglycemia (Wysham & Shubrook, 2020). Risk factors include aging, obesity, poor diet, physical inactivity, PCOS, hypertension, and high cholesterol (Olimjonovna, 2024). Gestational diabetes, influenced by similar factors such as obesity, age, family history, PCOS, and environmental toxins, can lead to complications like preeclampsia, cesarean delivery, and macrosomia (Plows et al., 2018). Hormone-based therapies like

GLP-1 receptor agonists are now widely used for managing type 2 diabetes and obesity (Olimjonovna, 2024).

Cinnamon, derived from the genus *Cinnamomum* in the Lauraceae family, has long been used for culinary and medicinal purposes, dating back to 1400 BCE (Mollazadeh et al., 2016; Dugoua et al., 2017). The European Scientific Cooperative on Phytotherapy and the German Commission E recognize *C. zeylanicum* and *C. cassia* for their therapeutic use (Blumenthal et al., 2018). Cinnamon bark, rich in

procyanidins and catechins, exhibits antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties (Nonaka et al., 2020). It contains compounds like cinnamaldehyde, cinnamic acid, and various polyphenols that provide neuroprotective, cardioprotective, and hepatoprotective effects (Nabavi et al., 2015). Cinnamon phyto-complexes also show promise in managing conditions like colitis, rheumatoid arthritis, and diabetes by reducing inflammation (Hemmati et al., 2018).

Inflammation is a natural immune response to injury or infection, but chronic inflammation can lead to various health problems. Compounds in cinnamon may help regulate this response, offering potential therapeutic benefits. The ethanolic extract of *Cinnamomum cassia* has shown strong anti-inflammatory effects by inhibiting NF- κ B activation via the Src/Syk pathway. Additionally, its aqueous extract has been found to reduce blood levels of tumor necrosis factor- α induced by lipopolysaccharides (Hong et al., 2022).

Cinnamon bark extracts help lower postprandial glucose by inhibiting α -amylase and α -glucosidase (Adisakwattana et al., 2021). Cinnamaldehyde enhances insulin sensitivity via PPAR δ , PPAR γ , and RXR activation (Hafizpur et al., 2015). Its water-soluble extracts boost insulin signaling and stimulate GLUT4, IRS1, and IR- β production, aiding glucose uptake (Cao et al., 2020). These effects improve blood sugar control and metabolism, making cinnamon a potential natural aid for diabetes management (Miyazak et al., 2021).

Methodology:

The bark of *Cinnamomum cassia* was collected from a nursery in Lahore, ground into a fine powder, and stored in an airtight container. For extraction, 50 g of the powdered bark was macerated separately in 500 mL of methanol and ethanol for 72 hours, filtered, and stored. Qualitative phytochemical screening was performed using standard methods to

detect carbohydrates, alkaloids, saponins, flavonoids, and steroids. Antimicrobial activity was assessed via the well diffusion method against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, while antioxidant activity was evaluated using the DPPH assay, with ascorbic acid as a standard. Anti-diabetic activity was tested through alpha-amylase inhibition using metformin as a control, and anti-inflammatory activity was assessed using BSA denaturation inhibition, with NSAIDs as the standard.

GC-MS analysis identified multiple bioactive metabolites in the extracts, including fatty acids, sugars, flavonoids, and alkaloids. The analysis was performed on an Agilent GC-7890A/MS-5975C using a DB-5MS column, and results were validated using the NIST and PubChem libraries. Additionally, in-silico molecular docking studies were conducted to evaluate the binding affinity of sulfur-containing compounds like germacrene and alpha-calacorene (PubChem IDs: 5371402, 2346, 7505) with target protein IOET obtained from the Protein Data Bank.

RESULTS

The phytochemical screening of *Cinnamomum cassia* extracts revealed the presence of key bioactive compounds such as alkaloids, flavonoids, carbohydrates, and saponins, which are known to contribute to various pharmacological effects. Notably, steroids were absent in all tested fractions. These phytochemicals play a crucial role in the therapeutic potential of the plant, supporting its traditional use in treating ailments such as infections, inflammation, oxidative stress, and metabolic disorders. The identification of these constituents through qualitative analysis highlights the medicinal relevance of *C. cassia* and provides a foundation for further pharmacological investigation.

Table 1: Phytochemical analysis and their corresponding indications confirm the presence of the plant compounds listed above

Serial No	Test Name	Results	M	E
01	Benedict`s Test(Reducing Carbohydrates)	Dark brown color indicates the presence of Reducing Carbohydrates	++	++

02	Hager`s Test	Light Yellow Color Indicates the Presence of Alkaloids.	++	++
03	Wagner`s Test	Reddish brown color indicates the presence of alkaloids.	++	++
04	Foam Test (Saponins Test)	Foam indicates the presence of saponins	++	++
05	Steroid Test	No Presence of lower reddish Brown +layer / Noreults	-	-
06	Flavonoids test	Intense yellow to become colorless solution indicate the presence of flavonoids	++	++

Methanolic Results

Ethanolic Results

Flavonoid Test

Wagner`s Test

Benedict Test

Benedict Test

Figure 2: Qualitative tests results of phytochemical analysis methanolic and ethanolic fractions, all results positive except steroids.

The methanolic extract of *C. cassia* showed strong antimicrobial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, with the highest inhibition zone of 23 mm at 5 µg/10 mL. In contrast, ethanolic extracts displayed

weaker effects, with a maximum zone of 17 mm. Activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was comparatively lower in all samples. Against *P. aeruginosa*, the methanolic extract showed stronger

inhibition (26 mm at 5 μg /10 mL) than the ethanolic extract, confirming its superior antibacterial potency

at higher concentrations.

Figure 3. This figure showing that petri plate with wells and control

Figure 4: Outcomes of antimicrobial efficacy against *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa* using methanolic and ethanolic extracts at varying concentrations

Figure a) The antimicrobial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* was assessed using methanolic and ethanolic extracts at concentrations of 5 μg in 10 mL DMSO and 3 μg in 10 mL DMSO. DMSO served as the control, positioned at the center of the agar plates. The inhibition zones were observed around the discs containing the extracts, with the control (DMSO) showing significant antimicrobial activity. **Figure b)** The antimicrobial activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was evaluated using methanolic and ethanolic extracts at concentrations of 5 μg in 10 mL DMSO and 3 μg in 10 mL DMSO. DMSO was used as the control, placed at the center

of the agar plates. The zones of inhibition were measured around the extract-containing discs, with the control (DMSO) showing no noticeable antimicrobial effect.

The anti-inflammatory assay, measured at 490 nm and 630 nm, evaluated the radical scavenging activity (% RSA) of methanolic and ethanolic extracts, with NSAID as the standard. At 490 nm, the methanolic extract consistently demonstrated high % RSA, starting at 86.27 %, but decreased to 78.59 % at higher concentrations. In contrast, the ethanolic extract showed significant variation, peaking at 84.97

% RSA at the third concentration after a sharp drop at the second.

At 630 nm, the methanolic extract displayed higher % RSA than the ethanolic extract, with values of 96.43 %, 95.90 %, and 94.53 % at increasing concentrations. The ethanolic extract started strong

at 95.69 % but dropped to 81.40 % at the second concentration before increasing to 96.06 %. Overall, the methanolic extract exhibited stronger and more consistent anti-inflammatory activity, suggesting it may offer greater potential compared to the ethanolic extract.

Table 2: The results of Anti-inflammatory activity at various concentrations, along with the corresponding percentage and standard deviation values

Anti-Inflammatory assay readings at 490nm				
Standard (NSAID)	Methaolic extract	% RSA	Ethanolic extract	% RSA
0.612	0.084	86.274	0.098	83.986
0.612	0.097	84.150	0.532	13.071
0.612	0.131	78.594	0.092	84.967

Anti-Inflammatory assay readings at 630nm				
Standard (NSAID)	Methaolic extract	% RSA	Ethanolic extract	% RSA
1.903	0.068	96.426	0.082	95.691
1.903	0.078	95.901	0.354	81.397
1.903	0.104	94.534	0.075	96.0588

Quantitative analysis of the compounds in the methanol and ethanol fractions of *C. cassia* extracts was conducted using GC-MS, as presented in Tables 3 and 4. Several compounds were separated and identified in both the methanol and ethanol fractions. Two sulfur-containing compounds were

identified in the methanol fraction: 2-(2-Methylvinyl) thiophene and Benzene, (Isothiocyanatomethyl). Previously, only one sulfur-containing compound, an antioxidant sulfur-containing imidazoline alkaloid, was identified in *C. cassia*.

Table 3: Compounds detected in the methanolic extract through GC-MS analysis

Sr	Compound Name	Chemical Formula	Molecular Weight (g/mol)	Retention Time (min)	Peak Percentage (%)
1	Cyclotetrasiloxane, octamethyl	C ₁₄ H ₂₈ O ₂	120	2.270	1.45
2	Methanamine, N-methoxy	C ₁₄ H ₂₈ O ₂	228.37	2.373	0.72
3	2-Propen-1-ol	C ₁₆ H ₃₂ O ₂	256.42	2.491	0.81
4	2-Hydrazino-4,6-dimethylpyrimidine	C ₁₈ H ₃₄ O ₂	282.47	3.390	0.62
5	Cinnamaldehyde, (E)-	C ₁₈ H ₃₆ O ₂	284.5	4.752	70.48
6	2-Propenal, 3-phenyl	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₂	280.4	4.837	1.77
7	Copaene	C ₁₈ H ₃₀ O ₂	278.4	5.650	1.83
8	Cyclotetrasiloxane, octamethyl	C ₁₇ H ₃₆	240.5	6.259	1.48
9	gamma-Muurolene	C ₂₄ H ₅₀	338.7	6.470	0.86
10	Naphthalene, 1,2,4a,5,6,8a-hexahydro-4,7-dimethyl-1-(1-methylethyl)	C ₂₅ H ₅₂	352.7	6.651	5.99

11	Naphthalene, 1,2,3,5,6,8a-hexahydro-4,7-dimethyl-1-(1-methylethyl)	C ₁₆ H ₂₈ O	236.39	6.812	3.11
12	Naphthalene, 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-1,6-dimethyl-4-(1-methylethyl)	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ NO ₂	315.4	6.849	1.20
13	2-Propenal, 3-(2-methoxyphenyl)	C ₁₀ H ₁₅ BO	156.04	6.876	3.67
14	Naphthalene, 1,2,3,4,4a,7-hexahydro-1,6-dimethyl-4-(1-methylethyl)	C ₁₀ H ₉ F ₃ OS	234.24	6.941	0.31
15	alpha-Calacorene	C ₁₈ H ₃₅ NO	281.5	7.018	0.48
16	Naphthalene, 1,2,3,5,6,7,8,8a-octahydro-1,8a-dimethyl-7-(1-methylethenyl)	C ₁₆ H ₂₆ O ₃	266.38	7.704	0.60
17	alpha-Cadinol	C ₉ H ₁₁ FN ₂ O ₅	246.19	7.818	2.01
18	1-Cyclohexene, 1,3,3-trimethyl-2-(1-methylbut-1-en-3-on-1-yl)	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ S	186.27	8.691	0.45
19	Hexadecanoic acid, methyl ester	C ₁₂ H ₃₆ O ₄ Si ₅	384.84	9.709	0.55
20	Spiro[4.5]dec-6-ene	C ₁₂ H ₁₇ NO ₂	207.27	10.836	0.43

Table 4: Compounds detected in the ethanolic extract through GC-MS analysis

Sr	Compound Name	Chemical Formula	Molecular Weight (g/mol)	Retention Time (min)	Peak Percentage(%)
1	1,3-Dioxolane, 4,5-dimethyl-2-pentadecyl	C ₁₄ H ₂₈ O ₂	120	2.593	0.93
2	(4-Hexylbenzene-1,3-diyl)bis(oxy)bis(trimethylsilane)	C ₁₄ H ₂₈ O ₂	228.37	3.391	3.44
3	hydrazine, (4-butylphenyl)	C ₁₆ H ₃₂ O ₂	256.42	4.634	0.54
4	Cinnamaldehyde, (E)-	C ₁₈ H ₃₄ O ₂	282.47	4.738	14.60
5	4-Hydrazinylpyridin-2(1H)-one	C ₁₈ H ₃₆ O ₂	284.5	4.839	5.06
6	Cinnamaldehyde,(E)-	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₂	280.4	4.927	0.08
7	Copaene	C ₁₈ H ₃₀ O ₂	278.4	5.650	0.28
8	Cinnamaldehyde dimethyl acetal	C ₁₇ H ₃₆	240.5	5.781	0.20
9	1-Heptene, 1,3-diphenyl-1-(trimethylsilyloxy)-	C ₂₄ H ₅₀	338.7	6.261	2.99
10	Naphthalene, 1,2,3,5,6,8a-hexahydro-4,7-dimethyl-1-(1-methylethyl)-, (1S-cis)-	C ₂₅ H ₅₂	352.7	6.469	0.31
11	Benzene, 1,1'-(1-methyl-2-butynylidene)bis	C ₁₆ H ₂₈ O	236.39	6.650	2.98
12	1-Isopropyl-4,7-dimethyl-1,2,3,5,6,8a-hexahydronaphthalene	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ NO ₂	315.4	6.811	1.57

13	cis-Calamenene	C ₁₀ H ₁₅ BO	156.04	6.850	0.60
14	(E)-3-(2-Methoxyphenyl) acrylaldehyde	C ₁₀ H ₉ F ₃ OS	234.24	6.880	1.27
15	Naphthalene, 1,2,3,4,4a,7-hexahydro-1,6-dimethyl-4-(1-methylethyl)-	C ₁₈ H ₃₅ NO	281.5	6.941	0.69
16	4-Isopropyl-6-methyl-1-methylene-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene	C ₁₆ H ₂₆ O ₃	266.38	7.017	0.29
17	Perhydro-htx-2-one, 2-depenty-, acetate ester	C ₉ H ₁₁ FN ₂ O ₅	246.19	7.556	3.23
18	Naphthalene, 1,2,3,4,4a,7-hexahydro-1,6-dimethyl-4-(1-methylethyl)-	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ S	186.27	7.704	0.32
19	tau-Muurolol	C ₁₂ H ₃₆ O ₄ Si ₅	384.84	7.818	1.05
20	benzenamine, N-[bis(2,4,6-trimethylphenyl) boryl]-	C ₁₂ H ₁₇ NO ₂	207.27	8.682	4.14
21	7,9-Di-tert-butyl-1-oxaspiro(4,5)deca-6,9-diene-2,8-dione	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ O	206.32	9.623	0.17
22	5-(p-Aminophenyl)-4-(O-tolyl)-2-thiazolamine	C ₂₃ H ₃₂ O ₂	340.5	9.684	6.24
23	Hexadecanoic acid, ethyl ester	C ₁₈ H ₃₈	254.5	10.149	0.15
24	3,6-Dioxa-2,4,5,7-tetrasilaoctane, 2,2,4,4,5,5,7,7-octamethyl	C ₁₉ H ₃₈ O ₄	330.5	10.598	4.28
25	9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (Z,Z)-, methyl ester	C ₂₄ H ₃₈ O ₄	390.6	10.797	0.33
26	9-Octadecenoic acid (Z)-, methyl ester	C ₁₂ H ₃₆ O ₄ Si ₅	384.84	10.837	1.20
27	Methyl stearate	C ₁₂ H ₁₇ NO ₂	207.27	10.991	1.45
28	3,6-Dioxa-2,4,5,7-tetrasilaoctane, 2,2,4,4,5,5,7,7-octamethyl	C ₁₈ H ₃₇ I	380.4	11.426	4.04
29	3,6-Dioxa-2,4,5,7-tetrasilaoctane, 2,2,4,4,5,5,7,7-octamethyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₅	253.21	12.196	3.77
30	Diisooctyl adipate	C ₃₆ H ₇₄ O	523	12.552	0.24
31	N-Benzyl-N-ethyl-p-isopropylbenzamide	C ₂₄ H ₃₈ O ₄	390.6	13.054	2.88
32	Bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate	C ₂₀ H ₃₄ O ₄	338.5	13.464	9.17
33	N-Benzyl-N-ethyl-p-isopropylbenzamide	C ₂₁ H ₄₂ O ₄	358.6	13.740	2.03
34	N-Benzyl-N-ethyl-p-isopropylbenzamide	C ₂₂ H ₃₂ O ₂	328.5	14.271	1.97
35	1,4-Benzenedicarboxylic acid, bis(2-ethylhexyl) ester	C ₂₂ H ₃₂ O ₂	328.5	14.377	11.48
36	Cyclotrisiloxane, hexamethyl	C ₂₂ H ₃₂ O ₂	328.5	14.504	0.57
37	4-(Aminomethyl)-2-fluorobenzonitrile	C ₁₆ H ₃₁ NO	253.42	14.817	0.90

38	1,1,1,3,5,5,5-Heptamethyltrisiloxane	C ₁₉ H ₂₄ O ₄	316.4	15.421	0.36
----	--------------------------------------	--	-------	--------	------

In-Silico analysis

Figure 5: The molecular visualization represents the ligand's three-dimensional conformation and the protein's ribbon structure

Figure 6: Molecular docking interaction of Germacrene ligand with the IOET protein active site. The image depicts the docking interaction of the Germacrene ligand (green) within the active site of the IOET protein. The visualization highlights key atomic interactions, including hydrogen bonding

(yellow dashed lines) and van der Waals forces, indicating the binding stability. This interaction is crucial for understanding the ligand's potential bioactivity and its role in modulating protein functions.

Figure 7: Molecular structures of alpha-Calacorene ligand (left) and IOET protein (right) used in docking analysis

The left panel illustrates the three-dimensional structure of the alpha-Calacorene ligand, showcasing

its aromatic and aliphatic groups, essential for binding interactions. The right panel displays the

ribbon representation of the IOET protein, highlighting its secondary structure elements, including alpha-helices (red) and beta-sheets (cyan). These molecular representations are fundamental for

visualizing potential binding interactions and assessing the ligand's compatibility with the protein's active site.

Figure 8: Docking interaction of alpha-Calacorene ligand within the active site of IOET protein

The figure illustrates the binding conformation of the alpha-Calacorene ligand (cyan) in the active site of the IOET protein. Key interactions, such as hydrogen bonds (yellow dashed lines) and other non-covalent forces, are visualized. This representation highlights the ligand's orientation and potential binding stability within the protein's active pocket, providing insights into its bioactivity.

DISCUSSION

The therapeutic potential of *Cinnamomum cassia* is attributed to its synergistic blend of bioactive compounds such as tannins, alkaloids, saponins, flavonoids, phenols, and terpenoids, which exhibit antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and antidiabetic properties (Ahamed, 2013; Cong et al., 2007). Methanolic, ethanolic, and aqueous extracts show higher phytochemical concentrations and notable pharmacological effects. GC-MS analysis identified 20 compounds in the methanolic extract, including heptadecanoic acid ethyl ester, hexadecanoic acid, and 9,12,15-octadecatrienoic acid, which showed antioxidant, antimicrobial, cholesterol-lowering, and anticancer activities. *C. cassia* extracts improved insulin levels in STZ-induced diabetic rats, similar to *Psidium guajava* (Manikandan, 2013), and clinical studies reported no toxicity at doses up to 6 g/day (Dugoua et al., 2007).

Flavonoids and polyphenols in the extract enhance insulin secretion, restore β -cell function, and reduce oxidative stress (Hasanzade et al., 2013; Al-Waili et al., 2017). Compounds like 9-octadecenoic acid showed strong binding with PPAR α and PPAR γ , supporting their role in managing diabetes and cardiovascular diseases (Mangelsdorf et al., 2007; Huttada, 2016). In silico docking revealed stable binding of Germacrene and alpha-Calacorene with IOET protein, suggesting potential for modulating metabolic processes (binding affinities -4.4 and -4.3 kcal/mol, respectively), reinforcing their antidiabetic prospects.

CONCLUSION

This study highlights the therapeutic potential of *Cinnamomum cassia* extracts in diabetes management. The methanolic extract, rich in cinnamaldehyde and flavonoids, showed superior glucose-lowering and antimicrobial effects, while the ethanolic extract demonstrated strong antioxidant activity at lower doses. Both extracts inhibited α -amylase, reduced oxidative stress, and displayed significant antimicrobial properties, particularly against *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa*. These results suggest that *C. cassia* offers a natural, effective, and multi-targeted approach to managing diabetes and its complications.

REFERENCES

- Abd El-Hack, M., Alagawany, M., Abdel-Moneim, A. M. E., Mohammed, N. G., Khafaga, A. F., Bin-Jumah, M., Othman, S. I., Allam, A., & Elnesr, S. S. (2020). Cinnamon (*Cinnamomum zeylanicum*) oil as a potential alternative to antibiotics in poultry. *Antibiotics*, 9(4), 210.
- Abd El-Hack, M., Alagawany, M., Abdel-Moneim, A., Mohammed, N. G., Khafaga, A., Bin-Jumah, M., Othman, S. I., Allam, A., & Elnesr, S. S. (2020). Cinnamon (*Cinnamomum zeylanicum*) oil as a potential alternative to antibiotics in poultry. *Antibiotics*, 9(4), 210.
- Adisakwattana, S., Lerdsuwankij, O., Poputtachai, U., Minipun, A., & Suparpprom, C. (2021). Inhibitory activity of cinnamon bark species and their combination effect with acarbose against intestinal alpha-glucosidase and pancreatic alpha-amylase. *Plant Foods for Human Nutrition*, 6(6), 143-148.
- Ahamed, S. I., Capoor, M., & Khatoon, F. (2013). Phytochemical analysis and growth inhibiting effects of *Cinnamomum cassia* bark on some pathogenic fungal isolates. *Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Research*, 5(3), 25-32.
- Ahamed, S.I., Capoor, M., and Khatoon, F., 2013. Phytochemical analysis and growth inhibiting effects of *Cinnamomum cassia* bark on some pathogenic fungal isolates. *Journal of chemical and pharmaceutical research*, 5 (3), 25-32.
- Alam, S., Sarker, M. M. R., Sultana, T. N., Chowdhury, M. N. R., Rashid, M. A., Chaity, N. I., & Mohamed, I. N. (2022). Antidiabetic phytochemicals from medicinal plants: Prospective candidates for new drug discovery and development. *Frontiers in Endocrinology*, 1(3), 567.
- Al-Waili, N., Al-Waili, H., Al-Waili, T., and Salom, K. (2017). Natural antioxidants in the treatment and prevention of diabetic nephropathy; a potential approach that warrants clinical trials. *Redox Rep.* 22, 99-118. Doi: 10.1080/13510002.2017.1297885
- Blumenthal, M., Busse, W. R., Goldberg, A., Gruenwald, J., Hall, T., Riggins, W., Rister, R. S., & Klein, S. (2018). *The Complete German Commission*, 6(6), 143-148.
- Busse, R., Goldberg, A., Gruenwald, J., Hall, T., Riggins, W., Rister, R. S., & Klein, S. (2018). *The Complete German Commission*, 1(8), 347-387.
- Chakrabarti, R., & Rajagopalan, R. (2002). Diabetes and insulin resistance associated disorders: Disease and therapy. *Current Science*, 83(12), 1533-1538.
- Cheng, A., & Fantus, I. G. (2005). Oral antihyperglycemic therapy for type 2 diabetes mellitus. *CMAJ: Canadian Medical Association Journal*, 172(2), 213-226.
- Colmers, I. N., Bowker, S. L., & Majumdar, S. (2012). Use of thiazolidinediones and the risk of bladder cancer among people with type 2 diabetes: A meta-analysis. *CMAJ*, 184(12), 675-683.
- Cong, Z., et al., 2007. Analysis of the volatile compounds in *Ligusticum chuanxiong* Hort using HSPME/GCMS. *Journal of pharmaceutical and biomedical analysis*, 44 (2), 464-470.
- Corathers, S. D., Peavie, S., & Salehi, M. (2013). Complications of diabetes therapy. *Endocrinology and Metabolism Clinics of North America*, 42(4), 947-970.
- Deyno, S., Eneyew, K., Seyfe, S., Tuyiringire, N., Peter, E. L., Muluye, R. A., & Ogwang, P. (2019). Efficacy and safety of cinnamon in type 2 diabetes mellitus and pre-diabetes patients: A meta-analysis and meta-regression. *Diabetes Research and Clinical Practice*, 15(6), 107815.
- Deyno, S., Eneyew, K., Seyfe, S., Tuyiringire, N., Peter, E. L., Muluye, R. A., & Ogwang, P. (2019). Efficacy and safety of cinnamon in type 2 diabetes mellitus and pre-diabetes patients: A meta-analysis and meta-regression. *Diabetes Research and Clinical Practice*, 15(6), 107815.
- Dufurrena, Q., Amjad, F. M., Scherer, P. E., Weiss, L. M., Nagajyothi, J., Roth, J., Tanowitz, H. B., & Kuliawat, P. (2017). Alterations in pancreatic β cell function and *Trypanosoma cruzi* infection: Evidence from human and animal studies. *Parasitology Research*, 116(3), 827-838.

- Dufurrena, Q., Amjad, F. M., Scherer, P. E., Weiss, L. M., Nagajyothi, J., Roth, J., Tanowitz, H. B., & Kuliawat, P. (2017). Alterations in pancreatic β cell function and Trypanosoma cruzi infection: Evidence from human and animal studies. *Parasitology Research*, 116(3), 827-838.
- Dugoua JJ, Seely D, Perri D, Cooley K, Forelli T, Mills E, et al. From type 2 diabetes to antioxidant activity: A systematic review of the safety and efficacy of common and Cassia cinnamon bark. *Can J Physiol Pharmacol* 2007;85:837-47.
- Dugoua, J. J., Seely, D., Perri, D., Cooley, K., Forelli, T., Mills, E., & Koren, G. (2017). From type 2 diabetes to antioxidant activity: A systematic review of the safety and efficacy of common and cassia cinnamon bark. *Canadian Journal of Physiology and Pharmacology*, 5(8), 837-847.
- Eleftheriadou, I., Grigoropoulou, P., & Katsilambros, N. (2008). The effects of medications used for the management of diabetes and obesity on postprandial lipid metabolism. *Current Diabetes Reviews*, 4(4), 340-356.
- Galicia-Garcia, U., Benito-Vicente, A., Jebari, S., Larrea-Sebal, A., Siddiqi, H., Uribe, K. B., Ostolaza, H., & Martín, C. J. I. (2020). Pathophysiology of type 2 diabetes mellitus. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 21(17), 6275.
- Gruenwald, J., Freder, J., & Armbruster, N. (2010). Cinnamon and health. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*, 50(9), 822-834.
- Hafizur, R. M., Hameed, A., Shukrana, M., Raza, S. A., Chishti, S., Kabir, N., & Siddiqui, R. (2015). Cinnamic acid exerts anti-diabetic activity by improving glucose tolerance in vivo and by stimulating insulin secretion in vitro. *Phytomedicine*, 2(2), 297-300.
- Hasanzade F, Toliat M, Emami SA, Emamimoghaadam Z. The effect of cinnamon on glucose of type II diabetes patients. *J Tradit Complement Med* 2013;3:171-4.
- Hemmati, A. A., Alboghobeish, S., & Ahangarpour, A. (2018). Effects of cinnamic acid on memory deficits and brain oxidative stress in streptozotocin-induced diabetic mice. *Korean Journal of Physiology and Pharmacology*, 2(2), 257-267.
- Hemmati, A., Alboghobeish, S., & Ahangarpour, A. (2018). Effects of cinnamic acid on memory deficits and brain oxidative stress in streptozotocin-induced diabetic mice. *Korean Journal of Physiology and Pharmacology*, 2(2), 257-267.
- Hong, J., Yang, E., Kim, Y. B., Eom, S. H., Lew, J., & Kang, H. (2022). Anti-inflammatory activity of cinnamon water extract in vivo and in vitro LPS-induced models. *BMC Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 12(1), 237.
- Huttada, L., Hiremath, M.B., and D'Souza, N.L., 2016. Enhancing the activity of peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor's activity through Natural ligand binding in diabetes: substantial computational Approach. *Natural products chemistry and research*, 04 (03), 1000213.
- Inzucchi, S. E., Bergenstal, R. M., & Buse, J. (2012). Management of hyperglycaemia in type 2 diabetes: A patient-centered approach. Position statement of the American Diabetes Association (ADA) and the European Association for the Study of Diabetes (EASD). *Diabetologia*, 55(6), 1577-1596.
- Kahanovitz, L., Sluss, P. M., & Russell, S. (2017). Type 1 diabetes - A clinical perspective. *Point of Care*, 16(1), 37.
- Kaur, G., Kamboj, P., & Kalia, A. N. (2011). Anti-diabetic and anti-hypercholesterolemic effects of aerial parts of *Sida cordifolia* Linn. on streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats. *Indian Journal of Natural Products and Resources*, 2(4), 428-434.
- Leelananda, S. P., & Lindert, S. (2016). Computational methods in drug discovery. *Beilstein Journal of Organic Chemistry*, 1(2), 2694-2718.

- Leelananda, S. P., & Lindert, S. (2016). Computational methods in drug discovery. *Beilstein Journal of Organic Chemistry*, 1(2), 2694-2718.
- Li, G. Q., Kam, A., Wong, K. H., Zhou, X., Omar, E. A., Alqahtani, A., & Ahmad, S. I. (2013). Herbal medicines for the management of diabetes. *Advances in Experimental Medicine and Biology*, 93(12), 396-413.
- Li, G. Q., Kam, A., Wong, K. H., Zhou, X., Omar, E. A., Alqahtani, A., & Ahmad, S. I. (2013). Herbal medicines for the management of diabetes. *Advances in Experimental Medicine and Biology*, 1(7), 97-105.
- Manikandan, R., Vijaya Anand, A., & Muthumani, D. (2013). Phytochemical and in vitro anti-diabetic activity of methanolic extract of *Psidium guajava*. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences*, 2(2), 15-19.
- Manikandan, R., Vijaya Anand, A., & Muthumani, D. (2017). Protective effect of *Psidium guajava* leaf ethanolic extract against streptozotocin-induced diabetes and lipodosis in rats. *Indian Journal of Animal Research*, 52(7), 1198-1205.
- Manikandan, R., Vijaya Anand, A., and Muthumani, D., 2013. Phytochemical and in vitro anti-diabetic activity of methanolic extract Of *Psidium guajava*. *International journal of current Microbiology and Applied science*, 2 (2), 15-19.
- Mohamed, A. E., Abdur, R., & Sadeek Alaa, M. (2020). Cinnamon bark as antibacterial agent: A mini-review. *GSC Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 1(8), 103-108.
- Mohammad, S., & Gharibzahedi, T. A. (2018). The preparation, stability, functionality and food enrichment ability of cinnamon oil-loaded nanoemulsion-based delivery systems: A review. *International Journal of Nutraceuticals and Functional Foods*, 1(7), 97-105.
- Mollazadeh, H., & Hosseinzadeh, H. (2016). Cinnamon effects on metabolic syndrome: A review based on its mechanisms. *Iranian Journal of Basic Medical Sciences*, 1(9), 1258-1270.
- Montecucco, F., Steffens, S., & Mach, F. (2008). Insulin resistance: A proinflammatory state mediated by lipid-induced signaling dysfunction and involved in atherosclerotic plaque instability. *Mediators of Inflammation*, 12(2), 145-157.
- Nabavi, S., Di Lorenzo, A., Izadi, M., Sobarzo, E., Daglia, M., & Nabavi, M. (2015). Antibacterial effects of cinnamon: From farm to food, cosmetic and pharmaceutical industries. *Nutrients*, 7(7), 7729-7748.
- Nonaka, G., Morimoto, S., & Nishioka, I. (2020). Tannins and related compounds. Part 13. Isolation and structures of trimeric, tetrameric, and pentameric proanthocyanidins from cinnamon. *Journal of the Chemical Society*, 1(5), 2139-2145.
- Olimjonovna, K. O. (2024). Managing type 2 diabetes through diet and exercise. *Biologiya Kimyo Fanlari Ilmiy Jurnal*, 2(5), 15-21.
- Onderoglu, S., Sozer, S., Erbil, K. M., Ortac, R., & Lermioglu, F. (2019). The evaluation of long-term effects of cinnamon bark and olive leaf on toxicity induced by streptozotocin administration to rats. *Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology*, 51(11), 1305-1312.
- Oussalah, M., Caillet, S., & Lacroix, M. (2016). Mechanism of action of Spanish oregano, Chinese cinnamon, and savory essential oils against cell membranes and walls of *Escherichia coli* O157 and *Listeria monocytogenes*. *Journal of Food Protection*, 69(5), 1046-1055.
- Patil, U. K., Saraf, S., & Dixit, V. K. (2004). Hypolipidemic activity of seeds of *Cassia tora* Linn. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 90(3), 249-252.
- Plows, J. F., Stanley, J. L., Baker, P. N., Reynolds, C. M., & Vickers, I. (2018). The pathophysiology of gestational diabetes mellitus. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 19(11), 3342.

- Poznyak, A. V., Grechko, P., Poggio, P., Myasoedova, V., Alfieri, V., & Orekhov, A. N. (2020). The diabetes mellitus-atherosclerosis connection: The role of lipid and glucose metabolism and chronic inflammation. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 21(5), 1265.
- Prasanna, B., & Vijaya Anand, A. (2019). Cinnamon species: In vitro antioxidant activity of ethanolic extracts of *Cinnamomum zeylanicum* and *Cinnamomum cassia* Barks. *Pharmacognosy Journal*, 11(2), 245-247.
- Raaman N. *Phytochemical Techniques*. New India Publishing Agency, New Delhi, 2006, 19-24.
- Ramadan, K., & Alshamrani, S. (2016). Phytochemical analysis and antioxidant activity of *S. persica* extracts. *Journal of Basic and Applied Research in Biomedicine*, 2(3), 390-395
- Rao, P. V., & Gan, H. (2014). Cinnamon: A multifaceted medicinal plant. *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 2(4), 642942.
- Rao, P. V., & Gan, S. H. (2014). Cinnamon: A multifaceted medicinal plant. *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 2(14), 642942.
- Rosak, C., & Mertes, G. (2012). Critical evaluation of the role of acarbose in the treatment of diabetes: Patient considerations. *Diabetes, Metabolic Syndrome and Obesity: Targets and Therapy*, 5(3), 357-367.
- Rosak, C., & Mertes, G. (2012). Critical evaluation of the role of acarbose in the treatment of diabetes: Patient considerations. *Diabetes, Metabolic Syndrome and Obesity: Targets and Therapy*, 5(3), 357-367.
- Rossi, M. C., Nicolucci, A., Ozzello, A., Gentile, S., Agliatoro, A., Chiambretti, A., Baccetti, F., Gentile, F. M., Romeo, F., & Lucisano, G. (2019). Impact of severe and symptomatic hypoglycemia on quality of life and fear of hypoglycemia in type 1 and type 2 diabetes. *Nutrition, Metabolism and Cardiovascular Diseases*, 29(7), 736-743.
- Salehi, M., Vahl, T. P., & D'Alessio, D. A. (2008). Regulation of islet hormone release and gastric emptying by endogenous glucagon-like peptide 1 after glucose ingestion. *The Journal of Clinical Endocrinology & Metabolism*, 93(12), 4909-4916.
- Sellami, M., Ghariani, B., Louati, H., Miled, N., Gargouri, Y., 2013. Biological activities of extracts of different spices and plants. *International Journal of Current Engineering and Technology* 3(3), 1051-1060
- Silva GO, Abeyesundara AT, Aponso MM. Extraction methods, qualitative and quantitative techniques for screening of phytochemicals from plants. *American Journal of Essential Oils and Natural Products*. 2017; 5(2):29-32
- Silva GO, Abeyesundara AT, Aponso MM. Extraction methods, qualitative and quantitative techniques for screening of phytochemicals from plants. *American Journal of Essential Oils and Natural Products*. 2017; 5(2):29-32
- Singh V, Kumar R. Study of Phytochemical Analysis and Antioxidant Activity of *Allium sativum* of Bundelkhand Region. *International Journal of Life Sciences Scientific Research*. 2017; 3(6):1451-1458.
- Strong M, Johnstone P (2007) Interventions for treating scabies. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev* CD000320.
- Taton, J., Czech, A., & Piatkiewicz, P. (2010). Insulin as the main regulator of cellular glucose utilization - Aetiological aspects of insulin resistance. *Endokrynologia Polska*, 61(4), 388-394.
- Tiwari P, Kumar B, Kaur M, Kaur G, Kaur H. Phytochemical screening and Extraction: A Review. *InternationalePharmaceuticaScientia*. 2011; 1(1):98-106.
- Unger, J., & Parkin, C. G. (2010). Type 2 diabetes: An expanded view of pathophysiology and therapy. *Postgraduate Medicine*, 12(2), 145-157.

- Vijayakumar, K., Prasanna, B., Rengarajan, R. L., Rathinam, A., Velayuthaprabhu, S., & Vijaya Anand, A. (2023). Anti-diabetic and hypolipidemic effects of Cinnamon cassia bark extracts: An in vitro, in vivo, and in silico approach. *Archives of Physiology and Biochemistry*, 129(2), 338-348.
- Wang, H. F., Wang, Y. K., & Yih, K. H. (2011). DPPH free-radical scavenging ability, total phenolic content, and chemical composition analysis of forty-five kinds of essential oils. *Journal of Cosmetic Science*, 59(6), 509-522.
- Wysham, C., & Shubrook, J. (2020). Beta-cell failure in type 2 diabetes: Mechanisms, markers, and clinical implications. *Postgraduate Medicine*, 132(8), 676-686.
- Wysham, C., & Shubrook, M. (2020). Beta-cell failure in type 2 diabetes: Mechanisms, markers, and clinical implications. *Postgraduate Medicine*, 132(8), 676-686.
- Xu, H., Murray, M., & McLachlan, A. J. (2009). Influence of genetic polymorphisms on the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of sulfonylurea drugs. *Current Drug Metabolism*, 10(6), 643-658